

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ПРОБЛЕМА ОМОНИМОВ В ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

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THE PROBLEM OF HOMONYMS IN LINGUISTICS

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Аннотация

Среди лексико-семантических групп слов тема омонимов занимает особое место в словарном запасе языка. Данная тема исследована в широком аспекте как в общем, так и в специальном языкознании. Из исследований известно, что отдельные исследователи в целом не пришли к единому мнению относительно омонимов и их положения в языке, типы, состав, определение, типы, омонимы и омонимы, омонимии и т. д. почти часто не совпадают или не совпадают. некоторые лингвисты не учли языковую особенность предмета при исследовании предмета. С точки зрения общего языкознания, некоторые известные лингвисты оценивают такие омонимы не как естественное явление языка, а как случайный случай. Например, всем нам известно, что известные российские лингвисты И.А.Булаховский, А.А.Реформатский, А.Н.Гвоздев и другие трактуют омонимы просто неправильно, они оценивают их как «патологическое» и «дефектное» явление, а не семантическое.

В некоторых случаях так же, как сравнивают полисемию с моносемией, сравнивают и омонимы с полисемией, что нельзя считать верным. Общеизвестен факт, что тот или иной вариант любого многозначного слова может отклоняться от своего первоначального значения и создавать многозначность с другим словом.

Кажется неправдоподобным, что все омонимы произошли от многозначных слов. Это также подтверждает наше мнение аргументом, который мы привели в статье. Некоторые наши лингвисты говорят, что омонимы в нашем языке состоят из одних и тех же частей речи. Это может быть на любом языке. Но факты доказывают, что омонимы в нашем языке могут состоять из разных частей речи.

Очень жаль также, что некоторые лингвисты в нашем языке считают омонимами, когда одна и та же нарицательная часть речи употребляется как личное существительное: Например: цветок-Цветок, Свободный-Свободный, Бриллиант-Алмаз, Милосердие- Милосердие, Добро-Добро, красивый – Красивый, желто-Желтый, черно-Черный, олень-Олень и т. д. Понятно, что такие слова имеют лексическое значение только как часть общей речи. Оно не имеет значения как личное имя, и поэтому они не могут быть омонимами.

В статье мы отметили, что некоторые определения омонимов в нашем языкознании ошибочны. Мы упомянули омофоны, омографы и омоформы, которые часто пишутся как виды омонимов, и отметили, что необходимо быть осторожными, называя их омонимами. Фактически они не нашли никакого выражения в определении омонима.

Abstract

The topic of homonyms has a special place among the lexical-semantic word groups in the vocabulary of the language. This topic has been widely studied in both general and special linguistics. It is clear from the studies that individual researchers' opinions on homonyms and their position in the language, types, composition, definition, kinds, homonyms and homonymics, homonymy, etc., often do not coincide, or some linguists did not take into account the language feature to which they belong when studying the topic. In terms of general linguistics, some famous linguists evaluate such homonyms not as a natural phenomenon of the language, but as a random phenomenon. For example, we all know that famous Russian linguists I.A. Bulakhovsky, A.A. Reformatsky, A.N. Gvazdev and others simply incorrectly approach homonyms, considering them as a "pathological" and "defective" phenomenon rather than a semantic phenomenon.

In some cases, just as they compare polysemy with monosemy, they also contrast homonyms with polysemy, which cannot be considered correct. It is a clear fact that this or that variant of any polysemous word can deviate from its original meaning and form polysemy in other words.

It does not seem convincing that all homonyms are formed from polysemous words. The argument we have brought in this article also confirms our opinion. Some linguists say that homonyms in our language consist of the same parts of speech. This can happen in any language. However, facts prove that homonyms can also consist of different parts of speech in our language.

It is also a very regrettable issue that some linguists, when talking about homonyms in our language, consider the case of the same general part of speech being used in the form of a personal name to be homonyms: For example: flower-Chichak, free-Azad, diamond-Almaz, mercy-Merhamat, good-Yakhshu, beautiful-Gozal, yellow-Sari, black-Gara, deer-Maral, etc. It is clear that these types of words have a lexical meaning only as a general part of speech. They have no meaning in the form of a personal name and therefore they cannot be homonyms.

We have also mentioned in the article that some of the definitions given to homonyms in our linguistics are flawed. We have also mentioned homophones, homographs, and homoforms, which are often written as types of homonyms, and noted that one should be careful in calling them homonyms. In fact, these have not found any expression in the definition of homonyms.

Ключевые слова: омоним, омонимия, полисемия, омофон, омограф, омоформа.

Keywords: homonym, homonymics, homonymy, polysemy, homophone, homograph, homoform.

Introduction

A lot has been said about homonyms in linguistics, their classification, lexical and semantic position, and the emergence and explanation of various terms related to them, but despite this, there are many controversial issues and disagreements among linguists related to this topic. V.V. Vinogradov rightly writes that "Before starting the analysis of homonyms and distinguishing their various types from each other, it is necessary to clarify the concept of homonym itself and distinguish it from related phenomena. He noted that a number of homophones attributed to homonyms by A.N. Gvozdyev, including those such as pila (saw) and nula (drink, drink, drink), are homophones, and that there are many contradictory and simply wrong things in all of them. [18, p. 299]. Russian linguists L.A. Bulakhovsky [3, p. 60] and A.A. Reformatsky [15, p. 61] had different attitudes towards homonyms. They perceived homonyms not as a semantic phenomenon in the language, but as a "pathological" phenomenon and a diseased layer of the language.

Along with V.V. Vinogradov [18, p.299], other linguists, including Galkinav Fedoruk [6, p.33-34], N.M. Shansky [16, p.21], S. Jafarov [8, p.15], N. Hasanov [7, p.43], B. Khalilov [9, p.163] consider homonyms as a lexical-semantic category, a natural phenomenon of the language. Indeed, homonyms have historically existed in the language as a semantic category, have been formed from time to time, developed and enriched. The explanation of the term homonym has not bypassed lexicographers either.

Thus, D.N. Ushakov [17, p.803] used homonyms in parallel with the term homonymics. [17, p.805] In contrast, S.I. Ojekov writes "Homonymy is a set of

homonyms and relationships between homonyms in any language." [14, p.1611]. In this regard, the idea given about homonyms in the "Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" is also interesting: 1. Homonymics is a section in lexicology that deals with homonyms. 2. A set of homonyms specific to any language.

The main part

The Azerbaijani language has rich homonyms. Homonymy is the correspondence of the sound of language units with different meanings. Phonetic homonymy. Lexical homonymy. Graphic homonymy. Syntactic homonymy.

Homonyms are different words that belong to the same part of speech and have the same sound composition: yel (patient) - yel (wind), kök (word root) - kök (plant type) - kök (fat man) [1, p.409]. Here, each of homonyms and homonyms has found a separate and different precise explanation. Even the explanation of homonym is given separately, it is noted that homonyms have the same part of speech. If we are talking about homonyms in the Azerbaijani language, we cannot agree with this idea at all. Because the words that make up homonyms in our language can have the same part of speech, as well as different parts of speech. If we are talking about homonyms in the Azerbaijani language, we cannot agree with this idea. Because the words that make up homonyms in our language can consist of different parts of speech. As in the example given in that quote: kök (word root) - kök (plant root) - kök (fat man) [1, p.409]. As you can see, while two of the homonyms here are nouns, the word "fat" in the phrase "fat man" is an adjective. Perhaps the authors meant homonyms in another language. Z.I. Kumarova correctly writes that "In fact, a homonym is a lexical

term in a language. Its study in linguistics has long been one of the main controversial issues. In fact, this issue should be taken into account and resolved within the framework of the national language." [10, p.46]. It is in this respect that homonyms, homonymy, as well as homophones, homographs and homoforms differ from those in other languages to one degree or another in terms of content and form. Let's take our language. While homonyms in our language consist of the same sound composition and different meaningful parts of speech, in Russian they refer only to the same part of speech.

The facts show that no matter how much is said about homonyms, this lexical category still exists in the language as a problem today. Thus, sometimes this lexical-semantic category has been treated as polemical. This is due, first of all, to the fact that in polemical terms, the meaning variants of the word are the same in terms of phonetic composition. Secondly, in polysemy, one of the different variants of the same word develops over time and, moving away from its initial variant, acts as an independent word and can form a homonym with any word in the language. However, those who identify homonyms with polysemy as a whole are in the wrong position.

Sometimes polysemy is compared with monosemy, and homonyms with polysemy, which is also unacceptable. Here, a mere change of term is observed. In fact, no lexical-semantic problem is solved by this. N. Mammadov and A. Akhundov, talking about the difference between a polysemous word and a homonym, come to the conclusion that "if different aspects of a certain concept are expressed, a polysemous word expresses different concepts, while homonym words are contrasted. [13, p.179] Here, as a rule, one cannot agree with the idea that polysemy expresses a concept. Polysemy does not express a new concept. It expresses different shades of meaning of any word. Homonyms express separate concepts.

According to A. Demirchizade, "as human consciousness changes and new concepts arise, new means of expression are also created for them. The creation of a new form for the expression of each new concept requires a lot of time, therefore, the previous means of expression are temporarily used for the new content, and thus, initially, polysemantic words and homonyms arise from here". [4, pp. 143-144]. In my opinion, one cannot fully agree with this idea. From here, the following conclusion is drawn that all homonyms in the language are supposedly the result of polysemanticity. It is from this point of view that A. Alekperov correctly answers A. Demirchizade's wrong idea in the following way. 1. Consciousness and language, concept and word are not taken in dialectical unity. 2. The division of a certain entity into smaller parts, its understanding and naming, does not arise from logical and psychological factors, but from the need for communication related to socio-historical conditions and the labor process. 3. People have not always felt the need to create a special word for each concept. Likewise, there is no "temporality" in the fact that previous means of expression also serve new concepts. [2, pp. 107-108] These broad and specific arguments brought by the author do not belong

only to A. Demirchizadeh, but are a consistent and definitive answer to all those who believe that homonyms in linguistics are created on the basis of polysemous words.

The definitions given to homonyms in Azerbaijani linguistics also differ from each other to one degree or another. "Homonyms are words with the same sound composition that express concepts that are unrelated to each other and have long since lost their meaning." [9, pp. 163-165]. It cannot be considered correct to accept the sentence "concepts that have long since lost their meaning" in its full sense. Homonyms do not consist of words that have lost their meaning as a whole. A certain part of them can be accepted as words that have lost their meaning, which we mentioned at the beginning of our article. In addition, the source we cited by B. Khalilov considers the same common noun as well as a proper noun to be homonyms. For example: azad-Azad, almaz-Almaz, yashchi-Yakhshi, kara-Qara, maral-Maral, jeyran-Jeyran, gözəl-Gözəl, etc. It is wrong to use the same common word in a language as a proper noun and accept it as a homonym. Personal names formed from the same common noun do not have any lexical meaning. Khalilov's idea that the second of the homonyms "bagh-bagh" is a loanword (supposedly meaning apple tree in Persian) is also absurd. F.Efendiyeva correctly denies homonymization due to personal names. [5, pp.59-60].

H. Hasanov's definition of homonym also sounds a bit strange. "Homonyms are words with different lexical meanings, the same grammatical meanings, but different, with the same phonetic composition, and indistinguishable pronunciation and spelling. [7, pp. 43-44]. If you refine this definition, maybe it can be grammatically reduced to a sentence, or it cannot be accepted as such. Studies prove that "the necessity of historical-etymological and semiotic studies in the work of determining homonyms is of great importance."

Nabatlı Gulamoğlu, in his article "Teaching Homonyms and Some Related Problems", expresses a very strange idea about homonyms. The study of homonyms in lexicology is of a conditional nature. In fact, even if only partially, the study of homonyms in lexicology is also of a conditional nature.

Considering all this, we come to the conclusion that the Russian linguists V. Vinogradov, O. S. Akhmanova, M. N. Fomina, and the Azerbaijani linguists A. Demirchizade, S. Jafarov, H. Hasanov, B. Khalilov consider the most important thing for homonyms to be the same phonetic composition and the diversity of meaning. As can be seen, although these linguists have explained homonyms in one way or another, in fact the general conclusion they have come to is the same.

There is no specific, completely universal criterion for accurately and comprehensively defining homonyms in a language. It is important to note that although homonyms are a historical category, their analysis should be approached according to the requirements of each era. From the point of view of modernity, they should be studied and studied in a synchronous plan. On the condition that historicity should not be forgotten.

Often, in linguistics, homonyms are divided and analyzed in two directions: a) basic homonyms, b) accidental homonyms. Some linguists explain those that are outside the basic homonyms as accidental, others as homonymous phenomena or types of homonyms. Sometimes these are characterized as types of homonymy. V. Vinogradov, however, disagreed with these ideas and wrote: "We confuse homonyms with various types of homophony. Homophony is a broader concept than homonymy. It includes all these types. We also sometimes encounter homonyms being confused with paronyms in linguistics. Homonyms are words that have the same spelling – that is, phonetic composition and pronunciation – but different lexical-semantic meanings. The words that constitute homonyms can be both the same and different in terms of parts of speech in our language.

Paronyms, although they are similar only in terms of pronunciation, are not identical to each other, and in terms of meaning they partially or not at all coincide. Therefore, it is often written that words that differ only in one sound are called paronyms. For example, see-art, table-surface, product-responsible, xeyr-xeyr, life-life.

It is very surprising that Turkan khanum Efendiyeva, a researcher of the lexical stylistics of our language, calls paronymous words such as "bagh-bax", "dagh-tagh", "ad-at" at the same time homophones [5, p.60]. S. Jafarov includes such words in the group of words formed by the "worm-worm" lexical way. [8, p.15]. After all, which of these are words formed by the lexical way? These are simply separate lexical units and belong to a kind of paronyms. These types of words have historically been formed independently in our language as a form of manifestation of a social phenomenon. They do not bear any signs of homonymy. Unfortunately, such controversial issues have not yet found their full boundaries and solutions in linguistics. In particular, different linguists have approached homophones, homographs and homoforms, which are considered types of homonymy, in different ways.

B. Khalilov and others explain homophones, homophores and homographs under the heading "Types of homonyms". [9, p.163]. H. Hasanov [7, p.109], and T. Efendiyeva [5, p.59-60] examine them under the heading "phonetic phenomenon". In contrast, S. Jafarov writes about this as follows: "In addition to lexical homonyms, there are also lexical units in our language that undergo certain morphological changes and acquire other characteristics. These can be divided into homographs, homophones, homoforms and lexico-grammatical types. These are also called word groups similar to homonyms. It would be more appropriate to call them accidental homonyms.

Mahira Naghigizi Huseynova, speaking about the stylistic aspects of homonyms, writes: "Focusing on the possibilities of phonetically meaningful homonym words, ashug and folk poets include these means of expression as a regular occurrence in the subject, in accordance with the emotional-expressive essence of the subject:

I am in love with mountains and mountains,
Standing on mountains and rocks.
Fate struck and struck,

Look at the pains and pains in my chest. (Ashug Fatulla)"

Poetic homonyms also differ with their colorful meaning in the couplet of Ashug Alasgar, .

Soul, you have fallen into the sea of love,
Keep delicate, shake delicate, sail delicate.

If we make you a gardener, my friend,
Don't let him receive, pick, smell the flower, pick delicate.

Here, "narın" in the first line is cautious, and "narın" in the second line is a case and affiliation suffix in the lexico-grammatical form, meaning to drink, and with the word "uz" meaning to tear off, he created a lexico-grammatical homonym with the word "uz" meaning to tear off. [11, p.13-14]

Opened my writing,
my talk, my saz (musical instrument).
Show your courage,
Let me write a poem.

The folk poet S. Vurgun created a beautiful pun with the homonyms "yazim"- "yazim" (my writings) in this poem. From this we come to the conclusion that homonyms are the most convenient means of creating puns in artistic language. It is no coincidence that in medieval Sufi ghazals and in our folk poets, puns from homonyms are widely spread in rhyme.

My darling, to the side of eye
From pain the eyes are yellow
Due their ways - yellow
Looking at their ways
The eyes have been yellow.

Homonym puns are of great importance in increasing the poetic diversity of the poem and its artistic quality.

Conclusion

After all, homophones, homographs, homoforms are not homonyms, and they have not even found expression in the definition of homonyms. In our opinion, it is worth thinking about this. Homonyms are of special importance in our artistic language with their own stylistic nuances. Homonyms, which are the product of artistic thinking in the figurative expression of thought, attract attention not only with their imagery, but also with their harmony and emotional-expressiveness. It can be said that in all examples of artistic language, from oral folk literature to written artistic language texts, such homonyms attract attention with their special stylistic diversity.

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